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ABSTRACTS

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A wearable microfluidics sensing system for non-invasive monitoring of multi-analytes

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Abstract: The introduction of point-of-care (POC) monitoring devices nowadays have greater influence in biomedical diagnosis and monitoring of disease progression and treatment. Microfluidics plays a critical role in biosensing by enabling precise manipulation and analysis of tiny amounts of fluids. This technology revolutionizes how we detect and analyse biomolecules, offering higher sensitivity, reduced reagent consumption, faster reactions, and the integration of multiple assays on compact platforms. Here, we try to provide a paradigm of on-demand, entirely non-invasive diagnostics that may replace routine blood-based laboratory testing for identification of diseases. The integration of microfluidics into wearable POC device allows for continuous monitoring of biomarkers present in biofluids, at the periphery of the human body. Creating effective microfluidic devices necessitates dealing with intricate design details that can be provided using COMSOL Multiphysics, a comprehensive and user-friendly simulation platform, to design and optimize microfluidic structures. This involves exploring diverse microchannel geometries and fluid flow rates, as well as predicting the behaviour of analytes within biofluids. The simulation-based approach streamlines the development process, ensuring efficiency and accuracy in system design. The study aims to contribute to the creation of compact fluid-based systems for precise analysis of biofluids, ultimately aiding in the prognosis of chronic diseases. The outcomes of this research could significantly advance the capabilities of POC devices, offering improved patient care and diagnostic accuracy.

Keywords: Sweat, wearable device, microfluidics, osteoporosis, COMSOL Multiphysics.

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